

Supporting Information

Positionality statement:

This paper is based on the personal experiences of the authors. Our author team encompasses a broad range of lived experiences and queer and trans identities, but does not claim to be comprehensive or representative of all queer and trans microbiologists. Additional perspectives, insights, and feedback were contributed by Queer and Trans in Microbiology Consortium members. The identities below were polled using a free response form, allowing authors to highlight any aspects of their identities they wished to.

All authors fall under the umbrella of LGBTQ+, with gender identities including nonbinary, genderqueer, genderfluid, woman of transgender experience, trans woman, man of transgender experience, cis male, and cis woman; and sexualities including queer, bisexual, pansexual, lesbian, homosexual, and gay. Of the 15 listed authors, 10 identify as trans, non-binary, genderqueer, and/or genderfluid. Our author list also includes identities such as Afro-Brazilian, Afro-Caribbean, Asian American, Black, Chinese, Cuban, Hispanic, Japanese, Jewish, Puerto-Rican, white, neurodivergent, disabled, trans-racial adoptee, able-bodied, and first-generation. The authors are predominantly United States of America nationals, with additional nationalities including Brazilian, Chinese, Israeli, Jamaican, and Puerto Rican.

The authors are all early-career, including researchers, post-doctoral researchers, graduate students, laboratory technicians, and early career faculty, based in primarily academic institutions as well as government, predominantly in the United States of America as well as the United Arab Emirates, Brazil, and the United Kingdom.

Appendix I: Further resources and guides

General best practices for inclusion

- [Supporting LGBTQ+ geoscientists, in and out of the classroom by Downen and Olcott \(2022\)](#)
- [Supporting LGBTQ students by OSTEM](#)
- [LGBT+ Inclusivity in Physics and Astronomy - A best practices guide by Ackerman et al., 2018](#)

Trans-specific practices for inclusion

- [Creating a Trans-Inclusive Workspace by Thoroughgood et al., 2020](#)
- [Transgender Ally by the LGBTQ+ Student Center](#)
- [Action Tips for Allies of Trans People by MIT](#)

Language and pronouns guides

- [LGBTQUIA+ Inclusive Language](#)
- [A beginners guide to pronoun usage in the workplace](#)
- [Pronouns: A Guide for the American University Community](#)

Inclusion practices for scientists with disabilities, chronic illness, and/or neurodiversity

- [Nothing About Us Without Us – Towards Genuine Inclusion of Disabled Scientists and Science Students Post Pandemic \(2021\)](#)
- [How to Make Professional Conferences More Accessible for Disabled People: Guidance from Actual Disabled Scientists \(2018\)](#)

Additional guides for fieldwork and marine research

- [Gender inclusion at sea](#)
- [Best practices for LGBTQ+ inclusion during ecological fieldwork: Considering safety, cis/heteronormativity and structural barriers](#)